

EC Sixth Framework ERA-NET Project

EUPHRESCO 2

(**EU**ropean **PH**ytosanitary **RE**search **CO**ordination)

Deliverable 4.1 and 4.12

Tackling Phytosanitary Emergencies

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Context

EUPHRESKO is an ERA-Net funded within the 6th and 7th Framework Programme and aims to increase cooperation and coordination of national phytosanitary research programmes at the EU level. EUPHRESKO is a network of organisations funding phytosanitary research.

Beyond the ERA-Net project, it aims at creating a long term self sustainable network of funders. One of the key objectives of such network is to offer tools and processes to study emergencies, such as emerging pests.

Recent introduction and establishment of pests, e.g *Pseudomonas syringae actinidiae*, *Xylella fastidiosa*, show the need of a very reactive structure to organise transnational efforts for studying such emerging pests.

This deliverable aims at providing overall structure with identification of actions and type of partners, if a topic is prioritized along the different steps of the process of topic identification, prioritization, decision and initiation of a collaborative action between funders.

Questions that need to be addressed by the long term sustainable Euphresco network are highlighted.

Overall process for tackling emergencies topics in the framework of the Euphresco network

Stage 1 – Expression of an emerging problem

Aim of this stage: to alert on emerging problems outside the regular calls for topics

Tools to be developed: a public market place open all over the year that allows parties (e.g. funders, NPPO, experts, researchers, private companies, stakeholders and not only Euphresco partners) to identify emerging problems. An open web platform should be considered as an appropriate market place.

Points to be addressed: definition of what an emerging problem can be:

- only related to regulated pests or also non regulated ones
- only pests entering the EU or also those threatening the EU territory.

This definition is important as it would impact the numbers of topic submitted and the area of work of the Euphresco network.

International standards (IPPC standard setting <https://www.ippc.int/core-activities/standards-setting> , EPPO standards and recommendations, alert list /reporting EPPO& NPPO) and PH regulations (e.g. EU http://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/plant_health_biosafety/rules/index_en.htm) should be considered when defining an emerging problem.

Stage 2 – Evaluation / prioritization

Aim of this stage: funders to identify submitted topics as emergencies for their country (compared to the other Euphresco topics already running) and should be managed as such.

Tools to be developed: a set of prioritization criteria to make the selection (e.g. to illustrate possible economic, environmental, pathway impacts...).

This action was initially identified in deliverable 4.5, but it was withdrawn later.

Stage 3 – Consultation of NPPO

Aim of this stage: to collect information and opinions of NPPO concerned by the selected emerging topics (e.g. economic, environmental, pathway impacts...). This information may contribute to the prioritization of the project / topic.

Tools to be developed: documentation (procedure and form) for collecting the information and opinions of NPPO. An online survey / questionnaire addressed to the concerned NPPO should be preferably considered for gathering easily and quickly the elements provided.

***Stage 4 – Identification of actions
needed and consultation***

Aim of this stage: to conduct thorough evaluation of the risk associated with the emergencies selected and identify the questions to be addressed within a Euphresco research project.

Points to be addressed: from available databases (e.g. EPPO global database) and experts:

- collect information available worldwide on the pest concerned
- generate specific biological/epidemiological data
- identify the national and/or EU status of the pest (e.g. present, under contingency / eradication).
- identify the risk of specific commodities
- perform a quick risk scan
- identify remaining questions / points to be addressed in the framework of a research project.
- collect an up-to-date list of research projects on pests of interest

***Stage 5 – Establishment of research /
experts consortium***

Aim of this stage: funders together with NPPO's to identify partners (researchers/experts) preferably involved (due to their expertise) in the project to answer the questions/points identified at stage 4.

Tools to be developed: access to experts databases (EPPO, EFSA, others) to identify possible partners of research project.

Consider to include in the market place area the possibility to record experts on pests / topics.

Points to be addressed:

- how to define that someone is an expert? Self declaration?
- which involvement of national reference laboratories, which also have expertise and contribute to the detection of emergencies?

Step 6 – Initiation of research project

Aim of this stage: to launch the project according to the Euphresco procedures outside the regular calls.

Points to be addressed: several barriers are identified for the initiation of such projects on emergencies as they can be initiated at any time.

- how to quickly fund a new project, especially if real pot is the only possibility to get the best expertise on the emergency topic?
- how to modify the national research work program ?
- for funders using the real pot or the virtual pot funding mechanisms, how to enable budget allocation to a selected research provider without an internal competition phase?
- for research providers, how to quickly liberate staff already involved in other projects (Euphresco or not)?
- how to improve the current procedures to enable very quick actions?
- how to join private research activities already running on the selected topic?
- how to appeal to EU funds for a Euphresco project if the emergency meets the criteria of the 882 rule (possibility of funding of sanitary action in case of emergencies) ? who is the interlocutor in this case (DG SANCO, DG RESEARCH)?

A questionnaire on possible barriers in such emergency topics directed to funders and research providers would help to better identify and lift some barriers.

Conclusion

This document presents a draft process to tackle the phytosanitary emergencies that EU member states may face. It highlights steps that should be followed to define if any topic identified as an emergency by a party should be taken on board by the Euphresco network and addressed through a research project.

For the future use of such process, different points should be addressed and clarify:

- The scope of an emergency in the framework of Euphresco topics.
- The development of public market place to collect emergencies topics
- The development of prioritization criteria to select relevant emergencies topics for further Euphresco project .
- The development or access to up-to-date databases on expertise (experts and competence) and research projects (ideally at international level to identify research performed on specific pests).
- The conditions for quick funding of transnational projects, especially through the funding route identified as “real pot”, to reach the best expertise.
- The connection with EU rules and mechanisms, especially in the framework of the future EU plant health regime and the revised EU 882 rule.
- The roles and responsibilities of the governing bodies of the Euphresco long term network.